

TENSILE PROPERTIES OF CARBON NANOTUBES-SHEETS/CARBON FIBERS/EPOXY AND CARBON NANOTUBES-GRAFTED CARBON FIBERS/EPOXY HYBRID COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

An interesting technique for modifying the carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites is hybridizing with carbon nanotubes (CNT). CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers offer potential benefits of nanoscale reinforcement to the well-established fibrous composites by creating multiscale hybrid micro-nano composites. However, the mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced with the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers have not been evaluated. It is important to clarify the tensile properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced with the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers. In this study, the tensile properties of carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites incorporating CNT-sheets (CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites) and CNT-grafted carbon fibers (CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites) were investigated. For the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, the tensile modulus of hybrid composites was higher than that in the as-received state. The tensile strength of CNT-sheets/polyacrylonitrile (PAN)-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composite was lower than that in the as-received state and the tensile strength of CNT-sheets/pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composite was higher than that in the as-received state. On the other hand, for the CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, the tensile modulus of hybrid composites was higher than that in the as-received state and tensile strength of hybrid composites was almost similar to that in as-received state.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNT), including single-wall carbon nanotubes (SWCNT), double-walled carbon nanotubes (DWCNT), a few-walled carbon nanotubes (FWCNT), and multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT), attract considerable attention and show great potential for various applications since their discovery. CNT are also desired fillers to improve the performance of polymers, and the use of CNT in polymer matrix composites has been a focus for academic researchers and engineers in recent years. However, a number of challenges must be met before CNT are exploited for envisioned applications to polymers. For example, CNT are generally entangled together and tend to agglomerate in polymers as bundles, ropes, particles (low volume fraction and dispersion quality), and the

randomly oriented discontinuous reinforcements may not fully take advantage of the superior properties of CNT.

Recently, great efforts have been undertaken to synthesize millimeter-scale aligned CNT arrays for production of large-scale CNT structures [1]. In particular, Inoue et al. [2] reported a rapid, simple, and cost effective method to grow vertically aligned and spinnable MWCNT-arrays. With this optimization in vertically aligned CNT growth, horizontally long-aligned CNT-sheets in macroscopic lengths have easily produced. Based on a solid-state drawing technique, Zhang et al. [3] created highly oriented, continuous and free-standing CNT-sheets with meter-long from CNT forest. Inoue et al. [4] fabricated successfully large-scale anisotropic well-aligned CNT-sheets by stacking and shrinking long-lasting MWCNT webs without binder materials. The aligned CNT-sheets could allow production of high volume fraction composites with desirable characteristics [5, 6].

Another interesting technique for modifying the surface of carbon fibers is grafting with CNT. The grafting of CNT on carbon fibers has been reported in the literature [7, 8]. CNT can be grown on the carbon fibers by chemical vapor deposition (CVD) [7] and electrodeposition (EPD) [8], among other methods. However, the effect of CNT grafting on the mechanical properties of carbon fiber has not been fully evaluated. Naito et al. [9-12] reported that CNT grafting improves the tensile strength, Weibull modulus, and thermal conductivity of high-strength PAN-based and high-modulus pitch-based carbon fibers.

The combination of CNT grafting benefits from the microscale reinforcement provided by traditional microscale fibers and the complementary nanoscale reinforcement offered by CNT. CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers offer potential benefits of nanoscale reinforcement to the well-established fibrous composites by creating multiscale hybrid micro-nano composites. However, the mechanical properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced with the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers have not been evaluated. It is important to clarify the tensile properties of polymer matrix composites reinforced with the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers and CNT-grafted carbon fibers.

In this study, the tensile properties and fracture behavior of carbon fiber reinforced polymer matrix composites incorporating CNT-sheets (CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites) and CNT-grafted carbon fibers (CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites) were investigated using epoxy-impregnated bundle-composites.

2 EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

2.1 Material

Carbon fibers used in this study are a high tensile strength PAN-based (T1000GB) and a high modulus pitch-based (K13D) carbon fiber. The T1000GB PAN-based carbon fiber was supplied from Toray Industries, Inc. and the K13D pitch-based carbon fiber was supplied from Mitsubishi Plastics, Inc. Note that as received, both fibers had been subjected to commercial surface treatments and sizing. The physical properties of both types of carbon fibers are summarized in Table 1.

	High strength PAN-based (T1000GB: T1000GB-12000-40D)		High modulus pitch-based (K13D: K13D2U)	
	As-received	CNT sheet/ CNT-grafted	As-received	CNT sheet/ CNT-grafted
Physical properties of carbon fiber				
Filaments (Count)	12000	-	2000	-
Yield <i>Tex</i> (g/1000m)	485	-	365	-
Density ρ_f (g/cm ³)	1.80	-	2.20	-
Tensile properties of CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composite				
Tensile strength σ_{bf} (GPa)	5.29 (0.30)	5.08 (0.37) [$N_p=10$] 4.79 (0.40) [$N_p=20$]	2.66 (0.21)	2.71 (0.22) [$N_p=10$] 2.79 (0.24) [$N_p=20$]
Tensile modulus	294 (12)	296 (10) [$N_p=10$]	937 (118)	938 (121) [$N_p=10$]

E_b (GPa)		299 (12) [$N_p=20$]		942 (104) [$N_p=20$]
Weibull modulus	19.24	14.66 [$N_p=10$]	13.11	12.83 [$N_p=10$]
m_b		12.73 [$N_p=20$]		12.22 [$N_p=20$]
Tensile properties of CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composite				
Tensile strength σ_{bf} (GPa)	5.29 (0.30)	5.31 (0.24)	2.66 (0.21)	2.67 (0.18)
Tensile modulus E_b (GPa)	294 (12)	297 (18)	937 (118)	941 (111)
Weibull modulus m_b	19.24	24.81	13.11	15.13

Table 1: Mechanical and physical properties of PAN-based and pitch-based carbon fibers and CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites.

The solution of thermoset epoxy consists of a diglycidyl ether of bisphenol A (DGEBA) epoxy (JER813, supplied by Mitsubishi Chemical Corp.) and an acid anhydride grade hardener (HY306, supplied by Mitsubishi Chemical Corp.) at a ratio of epoxy : hardener = 100 : 124 by weight.

2.2 Preparation of CNT-sheet

Vertically aligned MWCNT arrays were synthesized using a conventional thermal CVD system. An unprocessed substrate of quartz or oxidized Si was placed in the growth chamber. Details of the growth method are described in Ref. [2]. Iron chloride, $FeCl_2$, and acetylene, C_2H_2 were used as the precursor for a Fe catalyst and carbon source. The advantages of this method are rapid CNT growth rate of over 0.1 mm/min and a reaction efficiency of over 50 % with acetylene. In addition, every as-grown arrays can be drawn without post-processing.

As-grown multi-walled CNT in this study have about 1.0 mm height and an average diameter of 40 nm [2]. CNT-sheets can be directly drawn from an MWNT array by using the dry-drawing and winding technique. The number of CNT-sheets (the number of winding), N_p in this study were prepared as 10 and 20-ply. The resulting materials were then examined using an SEM (Quanta 200FEG, FEI) at an operating voltage of 10 kV.

2.3 Preparation of CNT-grafted carbon fiber

To grow carbon nanotubes (CNT) on top of the carbon fibers, the T1000GB and K13D fiber bundles were treated with a $Fe(C_5H_5)_2$ (ferrocene) catalyst by thermal CVD under vacuum. Experimental details of the CNT synthesis technique can be found elsewhere [7, 9-12]. Prior to catalyst introduction, the carbon fiber bundles were heat treated at 750 °C for 1 h under vacuum to remove sizing. The growth temperature for CNT deposition was 750 °C for T1000GB and 700 °C for K13D. The CNT growth duration was 900 sec. The resulting materials were then examined using an SEM (JSM-6500F, JEOL) at an operating voltage of 5 kV.

2.4 Preparation of epoxy impregnated bundle composite

The carbon fiber and CNT-grafted carbon fiber bundles were impregnated using a liquid epoxy solution. For the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, the epoxy impregnated bundles were covered with the CNT-sheets. The N_p in both the PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were used for 10 and 20. They were cured at 90 °C for 3 h and at 150 °C for 12 h, with heating rate of 3 °C/min to form a rigid bundle composite. The high curing temperature excursions for long durations were applied to make sure the resin was completely cured.

2.5 Tensile test

The bundle composite specimens were trimmed to approximately 65 mm, and emery paper tabs were bonded to each end of the specimen to act as the gripping region during tensile tests. Tensile tests were performed using a universal testing machine (AG-series, Shimadzu) with a 5 kN load cell. A gauge length L of 25 mm and a crosshead speed of 5 mm/min were used. All tests were conducted

under laboratory conditions at room temperature (at 23 ± 3 °C and $50 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity). 30 as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composite and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composite specimens were tested. Likewise, 20 CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were tested.

The tensile test applies a load, P_b , as a function of extension, U_b^* , until failure. The tensile stress σ_b and tensile strain ε_b were calculated as follows:

$$\sigma_b = \frac{P_b}{S} = \frac{P_b \cdot \rho_f}{Tex} \quad (1)$$

$$\varepsilon_b = \frac{U_b^*}{L^*} \quad (2)$$

where S is the total cross-sectional area of the filaments in a bundle, which can be calculated from the yield, Tex , and the density ρ_f of the T1000GB and K13D carbon fiber (Table 1). L^* is the distance between targets (reference marks). The targets were marked on the bundle composites ($L^* \approx 15$ mm). U_b^* was measured using a non-contact video extensometer (DVE-201, Shimadzu). The DVE-201 extensometers were used to perform precise, non-contact elongation measurements using CCD cameras to capture digital images of test specimens.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1 shows the SEM micrographs of the CNT features for the CNT-sheets. The CNT can be highly oriented and horizontally aligned in the drawing direction in the lower magnification. However, the several wavy and entangled CNT were observed in the higher magnification.

Figure 1: SEM micrograph of surface view for CNT-sheets.

Figure 2 shows the SEM micrographs of the CNT-grafted T1000GB PAN-based and K13D pitch-based carbon fiber filaments. The CNT can be grafted nearly perpendicular to the fiber surfaces, and grown uniformly and densely on the fibers. The outer diameters of the CNT ranged from 30-50 nm for T1000GB and from 60-80 nm for the K13D fibers. The individual CNT can be interconnected with each other in the several positions, forming a three-dimensional network structure on the fiber surface.

Figure 2: SEM micrographs of CNT-grafted PAN-based and pitch-based carbon fibers.

Representative cross-sectional images of CNT-grafted T1000GB PAN-based and K13D pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are shown in Figure 3, which clearly demonstrates that

the individual fibers in the CNT-grafted fiber bundle are well-dispersed in the epoxy. Similar results are observed in the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites and as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

Figure 3: Digital micrographs of the cross section of CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites.

For the all carbon fiber bundle composites, the stress applied to the specimen was linearly proportional to the strain until failure. The tensile modulus, E_b is calculated using a least square method for the straight line section of stress–strain curve. The average tensile modulus of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, and the as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites are summarized in Table 1. The average tensile modulus of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were almost similar to that in the as-received state. This indicates that the addition of high-aligned CNT-sheets and grafting of CNT do not affect the tensile modulus of carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

The tensile strength of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, and the as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites, σ_{bf} , was calculated as

$$\sigma_{bf} = \frac{P_{\max}}{S} = \frac{P_{\max} \cdot \rho_f}{Tex} \quad (3)$$

where P_{\max} is the maximum fracture load of the specimen. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, and the as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites are summarized in Table 1. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-sheets/T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were found to be 5.08 ($N_p = 10$) and 4.79 ($N_p = 20$) GPa, which are 4.0 and 9.5 % lower than that in the as-received state. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-sheets/K13D pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were found to be 2.71 ($N_p = 10$) and 2.79 ($N_p = 20$) GPa, which are 1.9 and 4.9 % higher than that in the as-received state. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-grafted T1000GB PAN-based and K13D pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were found to be 5.31 and 2.67 GPa, which are almost similar to those in the as-received state (5.29 and 2.66 GPa). This indicates that the hybridization of CNT-sheets is effective to improve the tensile strength of high modulus pitch-based carbon fiber/epoxy bundle composite, while the hybridization of CNT-sheets is not effective to improve the tensile strength of the high strength PAN-based carbon fiber/epoxy bundle composite, and the grafting of CNT does not affect the tensile strength of carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

The results shown in Table 1 clearly indicate that there is an appreciable scattering of tensile strength for these carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites. The statistical distribution of fiber and composite strengths is usually described by means of the Weibull equation [13]. The two-parameter Weibull distribution is given by

$$P_F = 1 - \exp \left[- \left(\frac{\sigma_{bf}}{\sigma_{b0}} \right)^{m_{bf}} \right] \quad (4)$$

where P_F is the cumulative probability of failure of a carbon fiber bundle composite at applied tensile strength σ_{bf} , m_{bf} is the Weibull modulus (Weibull shape parameter) of the carbon fiber bundle composite and σ_{b0} a Weibull scale parameter (characteristic stress). The cumulative probability of failure, P_F , under a particular stress is given by

$$P_F = \frac{i}{n+1} \quad (5)$$

where i is the number of fiber bundle composites that have broken at or below a stress level and n is the total number of fiber bundle composites tested. Rearrangement of the two-parameter Weibull statistical distribution expression (Eq. (4)) gives the following:

$$\ln \left(\ln \left[\frac{1}{1-P_F} \right] \right) = m_{bf} \ln(\sigma_{bf}) - m_{bf} \ln(\sigma_{b0}) \quad (5)$$

Hence the Weibull modulus, m_{bf} can be obtained by linear regression from a Weibull plot of equation (6).

Figure 4 shows the Weibull plots of the tensile strength for the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, and the as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

Figure 4: Weibull plots of the tensile strength for the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites.

The Weibull modulus, m_{bf} of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites, and the as-received carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites are summarized in Table 1. The Weibull modulus, m_{bf} for the as-received T1000GB and K13D carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites were found to be 19.24 and 13.11, respectively. The Weibull modulus, m_{bf} for the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were calculated to be 14.66 ($N_p = 10$, T1000GB), 12.73 ($N_p = 20$, T1000GB) and 12.83 ($N_p = 10$, K13D), 12.22 ($N_p = 20$, K13D), which are lower than that in the as-received state. The Weibull modulus, m_{bf} for the CNT-grafted T1000GB and K13D carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were calculated to be 24.81 and 15.13, which are higher than that in the as-received state. The results clearly show that the grafting of CNT improve the Weibull modulus of tensile strength for PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites, while the addition of high-aligned CNT-sheets decreased the Weibull modulus of tensile strength for

PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The tensile properties and fracture behavior of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and the CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were evaluated. The Weibull statistical distributions of the tensile strength for the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and the CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites were also characterized. The results are briefly summarized.

(1) The average tensile modulus of the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy and the CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are also almost similar to those in the as-received state. This indicates that the addition of high-aligned CNT-sheets and grafting of CNT do not affect the tensile modulus of carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

(2) The average tensile strengths of the CNT-sheets/T1000GB PAN-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are lower than that in the as-received state. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-sheets/K13D pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are higher than that in the as-received state. The average tensile strengths of the CNT-grafted T1000GB PAN-based and K13D pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are almost similar to those in the as-received state. This indicates that the hybridization of CNT-sheets is effective to improve the tensile strength of high modulus pitch-based carbon fiber/epoxy bundle composite, while the hybridization of CNT-sheets is not effective to improve the tensile strength of the high strength PAN-based carbon fiber/epoxy bundle composite, and the grafting of CNT does not affect the tensile strength of carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

(3) The Weibull modulus for the CNT-sheets/carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are lower than that in the as-received state. The Weibull modulus for the CNT-grafted carbon fibers/epoxy hybrid composites are higher than that in the as-received state. The results clearly show that the grafting of CNT improve the Weibull modulus of tensile strength for PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites, while the addition of high-aligned CNT-sheets decreased the Weibull modulus of tensile strength for PAN- and pitch-based carbon fibers/epoxy bundle composites.

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